

BASIC MEANS AND METHODS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION FOR SCHOOLGIRLS

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Annotation. The article explores the features of the use of special tools and norms in the practice for schoolgirls aged.

Key words: *schoolgirls*, sports section, physical preparation, special running exercises, physical exercises, general and special physical preparation.

Introduction. The high level of performance and admiration of both the girls and women at the world championships has been the reason for the growing number of fans of this sport. That is why there are many types of track and field schoolgirls in the country - short, medium and long distances, high and long jump. A minority of high-performing schoolgirls are, however, positive in terms of promoting healthy lifestyles in the community.

The exercise of girls and women of all ages has two main purposes, one of which is to improve health and the other is to defend the glory of the republic alongside men in sports. It is known that the number of such women engaged in physical culture and sports is growing every year. Women are resilient and do well in the long run. Therefore, women's physical education methods are slightly different from boys' physical education methods.

Exercises to develop endurance, speed, and accuracy of movement are equally beneficial for both sexes of students, but strength training exercises for boys and agility and flexibility exercises for girls should be included in the daily routine. Most teenage girls and adult girls don't value exercise. They are not physically active enough. It is no coincidence that the physical capabilities of girls aged 13-14 years are much higher than those of girls aged 16-17 years, which negatively affects the formation of the body of women. The working capacity of girls and women is much lower than that of men. This, of course, is due to the anatomical and psycho-physiological features of the female body. Today, one of the most pressing issues in determining the amount of any physical workload for our female athletes is to take into account the structure and functional characteristics of the female body. If our masters of sports do not take this into account, the health of our female athletes may deteriorate, and they may even be disabled for life[2,5].

The training of highly qualified athletes and reserve schoolgirls in Uzbekistan depends on the coaching practice. Further training of such girls athletes for running sports, including the average distance of schoolgirls, depends on the effective structure of the training process.

Research goal. Improving athletic skills for 13-14 year old schoolgirls through the use of basic tools and techniques in schoolgirls.

Research methods. Analysis of the literature on the subject, pedagogical observations, tests. It is important to ensure the implementation of laws and decisions on the popularization of sports in the country, the development and implementation of measures for attracting the younger generation to sport. Quality organization of sports training in mahallas, secondary schools, sports schools for children and adolescents, taking into account the age, gender, interests, physical capabilities of those involved in the organization of sports clubs and classes - has a positive effect on future sports training [6].

The five interrelated processes of teaching sports techniques, teaching tactics, developing physical qualities, instilling moral and willpower, and providing theoretical knowledge are five aspects of a single process.

Depending on the age and training level of the athlete girls, the specifics of the track and field, the time and stage of the training, more attention is paid to some aspects of the exercise and less. For example, if an athlete who is just starting out should pay more attention to mastering schoolgirls and other training techniques, improve general physical training, the athlete should focus more on tactical skills and special physical training. If you spend more time preparing your overall and special base during the preparation period, you will be given more time for a special session during the competition. You can learn different aspects of your workout by doing the same exercise, but there are some aspects to which you can learn more [3]. For example, the physical and willpower qualities that sports techniques are taught are nurtured and nurtured. The main purpose of this exercise is to teach the athlete more control over the movement. So this exercise is more about teaching [4,5].

Special exercises are usually an element, part, or “linker” of several activities from this type of schoolgirls. They can be used with shells (balls, sandbags, dumbbells, shingles, packing stones, block luggage, etc.), that is, with handguns, rifles, gymnastics, ropes, etc. that is, they go on shells and play without shells. The selected track and field schoolgirls work in challenging conditions (softer winds, winds, rain) and battlefields. It is used for psychological training of the facilitators, instilling in them the will, increasing the level of physical qualities. Depending on how and where the exercises are performed, their fitness and impact on the athlete may vary. Development of the main physical qualities of the athletes (physical training) is, first of all, the process of comprehensive and specific physical development of the schoolgirls. Thus, physical training is divided into general physical training and special physical training. General physical training refers to the development of the schoolgirls, that is, the development of muscular muscles, strengthening the body's organs and systems, enhancing their functional abilities, improving their ability to control, increasing strength, speed, endurance, agility, flexibility, and deficiencies in body and body. the correction is provided. In order to achieve this, it is important to regularly exercise all body parts with the body's organs and systems involved in various activities[2].

Instruments and their Use in Schoolgirls for Schoolchildren aged 13-14.

№	Content	norm
1.	Special treadmill training. Raise your knees running, jerking feet, running from foot to foot jumping up and down, from foot to toe to jump (deer), to quail, to run. The hands are empty at the bottom of the quail and the arms are in the same position as the other running	1 x 30 m
2.	Acceleration (fast running) - gradually increasing speed to run.	3 x 50 m
3.	Normal running.	200 m.
4.	For the development of leg strength - jumping 2 feet 40 feet in succession.	2 x 40 m
5.	Run your knees up and down for	10 seconds.
6.	Run your knees up and down with varying weight.	3 x 10 seconds.

7.	Transfer the ball of ball to the ball jointly with the partner (2-3 kg behind the head)	20 times
8.	Jumping up the ball with a cannon ball	20 to 30 balls 2-3 kg
9.	Throwing the ball in front of the ball with both hands holding the ball	10-15 times. The ball is 2-3 kg.
10.	Length jumps	10-15 times
11.	Run from bottom start	3 x 30 m
12.	Three-dash jumps	4-5 times
13.	Repeat run	2 x 40-50-60 m
14.	Thrust the kernel with both hands downward. (weight 3-4 kg.)	10 times
15.	Climbing the rope.	2-3 times

Specific physical training is aimed at developing all the functionality of the athlete's body, all organs and systems, depending on what is required for this type of schoolgirls. For this purpose you will use the exercises and special exercises of the selected type of schoolgirls[6].

№	Tests	Control group				Experimental group			
		At the beginning of the experiment	At the end of the experiment	Growth		At the beginning of the experiment	At the end of the experiment	Growth	
				Absolutely	%			Absolutely	%
1.	Running 60 meters (seconds)	11,7	11,1	0,6	5,1	11,9	10,4	1,5	12,6
2.	Running 1000 meters	6:40,0	6:18.0	22,0	6,5	6:44.0	5:41.0	1:03.0	18,3
3.	Running and long jump (cm)	240	278	37	15.2	237	307	72	30,3
4.	Throwing a small ball away (m)	16	18	2	12,5	17	22	5	29,4
5.	4x10 meter sprint (seconds)	13,2	12,0	1,2	9,1	13,4	11,1	2,2	19,4

When we compare the growth dynamics of the indicators in the table, the experiment growth of test results in the control group during the study from the control group much higher.

When we converted each test to an absolute increase in test scores, the difference between the experimental and control groups became apparent.

For general physical training, additional general impact exercises are used, and specific exercises are used for specific purposes. However, general physical training also uses specific exercises to correct the deficiencies in physical development, bodybuilding, posture, and the like. Exercises that develop strength, agility, endurance, agility, and flexibility play a key role in general and specialized physical training. The same qualities reflect the ability of the athlete to act as a body and organ in the entire body [3].

In order to achieve comprehensive physical development, health, and success in sports, it is essential to develop and nurture the basics of physical and spiritual qualities. Developing and nurturing the basics of these physical and spiritual qualities is an important part of the athletic training [5].

In this regard, the pre-training period will be important, and will give the schoolgirls of the age group of 13-14 years a great role in the activities of the following training periods. During the initial training, it is advisable to plan the training process perfectly and without overloading the athletes. Physical training is an important factor in the initial training process, which is why this issue has been addressed in our study planning so that it can be used more effectively during the training process.

Conclusion. During the initial training, it is advisable to increase the resilience of middistance runners through the use of physical training tools, including endurance training and endurance training. For this reason, practical exercises on the development of endurance athletes in mid-distance athletic training, that is, during the initial training.

1. According to the results of the tests that represent the level of physical development during the initial training, it was found that the control and survey teams were underdeveloped in the track and field athletes, which included the same types of endurance.

2. Indicators representing durability, agility - strength, special endurance and special agility -were found to be 65 to 70 percent better than the control group. Consequently, the indicators recorded in the study group indicate the effectiveness of the physical exercise used by the students in this group.

3. It has been proven once again that the emphasis on the initial training period for middledistance runners has been proven. In summary, to increase the interest of students who are now embarking on schoolgirls, to do athletic training through a variety of exercises, to develop and develop their physical abilities, and then to focus their interest in schoolgirls. Carrying his body in exciting, optimistic methods is the basis for his future training of an exemplary, talented, talented athlete.

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